

Created by

Contents of Report <https://lipidomicstandards.org>, version v2.6.1

Direct Infusion Workflow	1
Overall study design	1
Lipid extraction	1
Analytical platform	1
Quality control	2
Method qualification and validation	2
Reporting	2
 Sample Descriptions	 2
Staphylococcus aureus / Bacteria / Cells	2
 Lipid Class Descriptions	 2
1) Hex2DG[M+NH4] ⁺ / Lipid identification	2
1) Hex2DG[M+NH4] ⁺ / Lipid quantification	3
2) HexDG[M+NH4] ⁺ / Lipid identification	3
2) HexDG[M+NH4] ⁺ / Lipid quantification	3
3) PG[M+NH4] ⁺ / Lipid identification	4
3) PG[M+NH4] ⁺ / Lipid quantification	4
4) PG[M-H] ⁻ / Lipid identification	5
4) PG[M-H] ⁻ / Lipid quantification	5
5) PA[M+NH4] ⁺ / Lipid identification	5
5) PA[M+NH4] ⁺ / Lipid quantification	6
6) LysylPG[M-H] ⁻ / Lipid identification	6
6) LysylPG[M-H] ⁻ / Lipid quantification	6

Direct Infusion Workflow

Overall study design

Title of the study	An anti-adhesive compound that modulates the production of Staphylococcus aureus cell wall-anchored proteins		
Document creation date	03/12/2026	Principal investigator	Georgina Cox
Institution	University of Guelph (samples) and Kansas State University (lipidomics)	Corresponding Email	gcox@uoguelph.ca
Is the workflow targeted or untargeted?	Targeted	Clinical	No

Lipid extraction

Extraction method	2-phase system	pH adjustment	None
2-phase system	Bligh&Dyer	Special conditions	2 hours of agitation of cell pellet after addition of chloroform/methanol (2:1) before pelleting and removing supernatant. 0.6 parts 0.9% sodium chloride added to supernatant to split phases, and organic (lower) phase was retained. Pellet was reextracted similarly but with shorter (15 min) agitations.
Derivatization	None	Were internal standards added prior extraction?	No

Analytical platform

Ionization additives	Ammonium acetate	Detector	Mass spectrometer
----------------------	------------------	----------	-------------------

MS type	QQQ	MS vendor	Waters
Direct type	FIA	MS Level	MS ²
Mass window for precursor ion isolation (in Da total isolation window)	1	Mass resolution for detected ion at MS ²	Low resolution
Resolution at MS ²	Unit	Recording mode of raw data at MS ²	Profile mode
Was/Were additional dimension/techniques used	No		

Quality control

Blanks	Yes	Type of Blanks	Internal standard blank
Quality control	No		

Method qualification and validation

Method validation	Yes	Lipid recovery	No
Dynamic quantification range	Yes	Limit of quantitation (LOQ)/Limit of detection (LOD)	Yes
Precision	Yes	Accuracy	No
Guidelines followed	None		

Reporting

Are reported raw data uploaded into repository?	Yes	Link to repository / ID to entry	http://dx.doi.org/10.21228/M8DP1W
Are metadata available?	Yes	Summary data	Quantification and identification data
Raw data upload	Yes	Additional comments	Dynamic range validated for PA and PG.

Sample Descriptions

Staphylococcus aureus / Bacteria / Cells

Storage and collection conditions	Unknown
-----------------------------------	---------

Lipid Class Descriptions

1) Hex2DG[M+NH₄]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	Hex2DG	MS Level for identification	MS ²		
Identification level	Species level	MS ² adduct	[M+NH ₄] ⁺		
Fragments for identification	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Fragment name</td> <td>+HG(Hex2+NH₃,341)</td> </tr> </table>			Fragment name	+HG(Hex2+NH ₃ ,341)
Fragment name	+HG(Hex2+NH ₃ ,341)				
Isotope correction at MS ²	Type 2	MS ² verified by standard	Yes		

Background check at MS ²	Yes	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes
Which assumptions were presumed?	Even and odd chains but no oxidized chains	Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap
Limit of detection	No	Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Background subtraction	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes		

1) Hex2DG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ²
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ²			
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
DGDG 18:0_16:0	-HG(Hex2+NH3,341)	DGDG	
DGDG 18:0_18:0	-HG(Hex2+NH3,341)	DGDG	
Type of quantification	Compared to line between intensities of two internal standards in spectrum	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	No	Limit of quantification	No
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	Homemade
Batch correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Note that internal standards are not well matched to sample in terms of type of sugar. Website used for quantification: http://lipidome.bcf.ku.edu:8080/Lipidomics/

2) HexDG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	HexDG	MS Level for identification	MS ²
Identification level	Species level	MS ² adduct	[M+NH4] ⁺
Fragments for identification			
Fragment name			
-HG(Hex+NH3,179)			
Isotope correction at MS ²	Type 2	MS ² verified by standard	Yes
Background check at MS ²	Yes	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes
Which assumptions were presumed?	Targeted identification of odd and even chains, but assumed no oxidized chains	Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap
Limit of detection	No	Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Background subtraction	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes		

2) HexDG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ²
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ²			
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	

MGDG 18:0_16:0	-HG(Hex+NH3,179)	MGDG
MGDG 18:0_18:0	-HG(Hex+NH3,179)	MGDG

Type of quantification	Compared to line between intensities of two internal standards in spectrum	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	No	Limit of quantification	No
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	Homemade
Batch correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Note that internal standards are not well matched to sample in terms of type of sugar. Website used for quantification: http://lipidome.bcf.ku.edu:8080/Lipidomics/

3) PG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PG	MS Level for identification	MS ²
Identification level	Species level	MS ² adduct	[M+NH4] ⁺
Fragments for identification			
Fragment name			
-HG(PG+NH3,189)			
Isotope correction at MS ²	Type 2	MS ² verified by standard	Yes
Background check at MS ²	Yes	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes
Which assumptions were presumed?	Target list with even and odd chains, but no oxidized chains	Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap
Limit of detection	No	Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Background subtraction	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes		

3) PG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ²
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ²			
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
PG 14:0_14:0	-HG(PG+NH3,189)	PG	
PG 20:0_20:0 (diphytanoyl)	-HG(PG+NH3,189)	PG	

Type of quantification	Compared to line between intensities of two internal standards in spectrum	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	No	Limit of quantification	No
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	Homemade
Batch correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Website used for quantification: http://lipidome.bcf.ku.edu:8080/Lipidomics/

4) PG[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PG	MS Level for identification	MS ²
Identification level	Species level	MS ² adduct	[M-H]-
Fragments for identification			
Fragment name			
GP(153)			
Isotope correction at MS ²	Type 2	MS ² verified by standard	Yes
Background check at MS ²	Yes	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes
Which assumptions were presumed?	Target lipid of even and odd chains	Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap
Limit of detection	No	Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Background subtraction	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes		

4) PG[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ²
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ²			
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
PG 14:0_14:0	GP(153)	PG	
PG 20:0_20:0 (diphytanoyl)	GP(153)	PG	
Type of quantification	Compared to line between intensities of two internal standards in spectrum	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	No	Limit of quantification	No
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	Homemade
Batch correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Website used for quantification: http://lipidome.bcf.ku.edu:8080/Lipidomics/

5) PA[M+NH₄]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PA	MS Level for identification	MS ²
Identification level	Species level	MS ² adduct	[M+NH ₄] ⁺
Fragments for identification			
Fragment name			
-PA(phosphate+NH ₃ ,115)			
Isotope correction at MS ²	Type 2	MS ² verified by standard	Yes
Background check at MS ²	Yes	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes
Which assumptions were presumed?	Target list with even and odd chains but no oxidized chains	Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap
Limit of detection	No	Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Background subtraction	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes		

5) PA[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ²
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ²			
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
PA 14:0_14:0	-PA(phosphate+NH ₃ ,115)	PA	
PA 20:0_20:0 (diphytanoyl)	-PA(phosphate+NH ₃ ,115)	PA	
Type of quantification	Compared to line between intensities of two internal standards in spectrum	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	No	Limit of quantification	No
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	Homemade
Batch correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Website used for quantification: http://lipidome.bcf.ku.edu:8080/Lipidomics/

6) LysylPG[M-H]⁻ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LysylPG	MS Level for identification	MS ²
Identification level	Species level	MS ² adduct	[M-H] ⁻
Fragments for identification			
Fragment name			
Lysyl(145)			
Isotope correction at MS ²	Type 2	MS ² verified by standard	Yes
Background check at MS ²	Yes	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes
Which assumptions were presumed?	Target lipid of even and odd chains	Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap
Limit of detection	No	Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Background subtraction	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes		

6) LysylPG[M-H]⁻ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ²
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ²			
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
PG 14:0_14:0	GP(153)	PG	
PG 20:0_20:0 (diphytanoyl)	GP(153)	PG	
Type of quantification	Compared to line between intensities of two internal standards in spectrum	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	No	Limit of quantification	No
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	Homemade
Batch correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Note that internal standards are not well matched to analytes. Website used for quantification: http://lipidome.bcf.ku.edu:8080/Lipidomics/

